
An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

Dietermar Say

College of Asia Pacific Studies, Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University, Oita 874-8577, Japan

ABSTRACT: Supporting community based-tourism (CBT) is a development strategy for local government to use tourism to improve local people's livelihoods. Here local government takes over the agenda for the community and supplies updates and resources on development but leaves the decision making to the community itself. However it is not just the government that designs CBT strategies, the existing literature shows that members of academia and international organizations have been carrying out, publishing and analyzing CBT case studies, thus providing more insight as to why CBT fails or succeeds in communities. In general, the tourism transformation achieved by government may not always be satisfactory to the community as opposed to academia, international organizations, or the community itself. As each community is unique, the present study examines the general attitudes of 535 respondents about government performance in CBT from 40 different countries. The respondents are divided into four groups according to the respondents' work experience with academia, government, international organizations, and the community. The results show that the government group sees themselves as the least productive, whereas the international organization group paradoxically sees the government's ability in CBT as the most favorable. The outcome of this study provides a general overview of the capabilities and limits of government in CBT development which may be of use to communities and stakeholders that are considering becoming involved in such transformations.

KEYWORDS: Community Based-Tourism (CBT); Government; Community Development; Community

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of CBT can be traced back to the 1950s, when the United Nations advocated this as a project that local government could be involved in to help develop their own communities. As this method became more popular, scholars, government, and international organizations would continue to write new CBT guidelines. From the literature review carried out for this study and outlined below, in this situation local governments would cooperate with non-government organizations (NGO) to formulate plans and guidelines for local communities to take part in tourism transformation programs. The problem is that CBT transformation has been recorded as causing negative impacts that are irreversible. From the literature review some 80% of the transformations have led to an unsustainable community, which leads the wider community to lose trust in the government and become dependent on external funding. Transforming a community into a tourist destination has its socio-economic benefits, but to reduce the risk, the involvement of academia and international organizations in addition to local government could bring better results than just relying on local government due to their greater expertise and experience in CBT development. This study evaluates local government's involvement in CBT development projects from the perspective of 535 respondents that have worked in academia, the government sector, an international organization, or a local community. The outcomes of this study will assist community members to better make decisions if their location should undergo community tourism transformation with the assistance of local government.

2. LITERATURE ON CBT AND REVITALIZATION

The concept of CBT is often misunderstood as being tourism that takes place in small or rural communities (Kontogeorgopoulos et al., 2014). But the primary purpose of such tourism transformation is in fact to build up local communities where management and ownership is controlled by local people instead of foreign cooperation anywhere (Kaur et al., 2016). The role of local government in CBT is to support community engagement and public affairs through neighborhood empowerment and

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

local government reform (DCLG, 2006). Although CBT mostly takes place in less developed places and is targeted to alleviate poverty and other problems, the concept of CBT shares similarities with the business concept of strategic destination branding and destination marketing (Tasci, 2011). Government and other agencies have the ability to modernize communities (Branden and Mayo, 1999), causing their culture to lose authenticity. Kretzman and McKnight (1993) think that the reason communities fail to develop can be because developers, government or NGOs presume that a troubled neighborhood can be improved by constantly pouring resources into it, not changing its fundamentals. Paradoxically, in not doing so the community's mindset can be changed so that they come to believe they themselves are the victims of the government despite all the money flowing in, and they become dependent on third party aid, instead of searching for methods to become self-sustaining.

One common stage in tourism development is the government's involvement in attempting to reform the community through gentrification. This can redevelop a poor or old community into a wealthier one, reformation of the community can bring better living conditions, and in the process, increase the real estate value of the neighborhood. It can rejuvenate locations with population shortages by attracting middle-class people into the community. Gentrification improves peoples' quality of life by rebalancing (Duany, 2001). Newcomers from the middle-class help blend and mix in with the lower class, because this means that there are more educated people, taxpayers, and consumption rates for the community (Duany, 2001; Byrne, 2003).

However, the phenomenon of physical renovation and social upgrading creates problems of displacement (Kerstein, 1990). Since it is a reinvestment of capital at the urban center for the purpose of producing space for the wealthy class rather than for the current occupants in that space (Smith, 2000). The phenomenon of physical renovation and social upgrading creates problems of displacement (Kerstein, 1990). Gentrification makes it more difficult for the poor that are struggling to afford houses (Green and Goetting, 2010). Overpricing, misplacement, and discrimination are the common drawbacks of gentrification (Kerstein, 1990; Newman and Wyly, 2006), but the benefits for the city outweigh the costs faced by the unfortunate poor (Sumka, 1990).

3. WHEN GOVERNMENT FAILS ITS COMMUNITIES

Even without tourism transformation there are existing records where local government's involvement in community development projects has created more problems. This is because, even if the government is responsible and accountable for running the country province or local area, modern developments are fast, complex, diverse, and difficult to micromanage from the center (DCLG, 2006). The role of government and external agencies is to understand and listen to the community's problems. Programs which ignore the community and are in favor of raising the economic status of a few run the risk of demoralizing the community well-being and other social structures (Wilkinson, 1979). Kretzman and McKnight (1993) mentioned that there are risks that the community will see themselves as a client and accept the status of their own neighborhood. A recurring problem with community development is that most development programs are designed and funded by external parties, and once the funding flow and outside assistance stops, the community will have a hard time to maintain its standards, therefore it is necessary for the developers to stay for a reasonable time span and monitor the community periodically so it can keep up its standards (World Wildlife Fund, 2001). Wilkinson (1979) stated that even though economic development should have high priority for the sake of the improvement of the delivery of social services, if resources and services are not evenly distributed this can result in a decline in community activities and well-being in uneven regions.

Meanwhile, resources given to troubled communities can lead to further over-reliance; local community leaders have in the past highlighted their problems when demanding more resources from NGOs and other aid sectors, yet the community leaders do not reflect on their own strengths that would allow them to change. The local community's relationship with their neighbors weakens as the locals cling on to the funders, experts, and social workers instead. The reliance on NGOs and funders deepen the cycle of dependency, and the programs tend to end when funding is short. It has been observed that communities that are helped and have overly relied on this help will always become worse and more intractable than other communities. This end product is the major cause of the sense of hopelessness in low-income neighborhoods (DCLG, 2006).

The DCLG has analyzed past unsuccessful community development case studies in the UK and found that the errors are often related to the following issues: (1) Little awareness that individual concerns can be affected by joint actions; (2) The disadvantaged are often the ones that suffer from poor infrastructure and cannot clarify their needs to authorities; (3) When groups are dominated by strong individuals who keep the power of decision making to themselves; (4) When community organization fails to adapt to change or misses funding opportunities; (5) When community leaders or representatives are not properly elected, causing unbalanced partnerships; (6) Different interests among groups and the inability to compromise leads

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

to poor decision making results; (7) When parts of the local population refuse to be involved due to prejudice and discrimination problems among the group; and (8) When public agents or governmental departments are unaware of community insights and this leads to passive resistance to development.

The reason why the poor remain poor is due to the trap of low or negative economic growth rates, they need to use all their income to merely stay alive on account of having almost no savings (Sachs, 2005). Poverty does not necessarily have to be associated with low incomes, inadequate resources such as lack of clean water, food, shelter, and other basic needs are all a form of poverty. It is a multidimensional problem and requires collective solutions, because eliminating poverty is just as relevant to development. Sachs (2005) mentioned that it is a misconception that laziness or government corruption is the main reason the poor stay poor, in fact the people suffering in poverty most often happen to live in geographically isolated regions and are vulnerable to disease and natural hazards

CBT has the ability to allow communities to grow and be more independent from external parties. While in some situations, communities would be better off without the government's interference. But without the government's support in building infrastructure and funding, community development is difficult to startup on its own. To examine this conundrum, the present study surveyed 535 online respondents with a CBT background to evaluate the overall performance of local government's involvement in CBT projects.

4. METHODOLOGY

As each community and government is unique in its own cultural and practices, an online questionnaire is preferred to collect respondents' overview of their evaluation of their own government. The targeted respondents are chosen based primarily on their work experience with the government and community. Furthermore, since there are also CBT guidelines written by academia and international organizations, respondents that have experience in working with these groups and have backgrounds in community development could provide a third party perspective for comparison. The survey design is based on a content analysis of 30 tourism plans written by governments and NGOs as seen in Table 1. The plans are chosen based on their step-by-step guidelines for promoting tourism to the community. These plans and guidelines were gathered and analyzed through the word cloud program, MAXQDA, to find the common traits of the government's role in CBT programs. The word cloud analysis shows that the most frequent phrases are action plan, community development, decision making, economic growth, international tourism, local communities, natural resources, private sector, product development, sustainable development, tourism planning, and monitoring. These keywords are used as key indicators for the survey items. Further observation shows how in the majority of the guidelines the procedure for CBT development involves 1) planning, 2) plan execution, and 3) monitoring and evaluation. The survey items are based on a 7-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Agree; 7= Strongly Disagree) to evaluate the local government's involvement, CBT operation stages, community understanding, and work interest between local government and its community, which can be found in Table 2.

Table 1: 30 CBT guidelines designed by the local government and NGOs

Community-Tourism Guidelines	Year	Designed for Communities
BLM (Bureau of Land Management)	2019	USA
City of Sydney	2013	Sydney
COBATI (Community Based Tourism Initiative)	2015	Uganda
DCLG (Department of Communities and Local Government)	2001	London
DED (Department of Economic Development)	2018	Dubai
DEH Department for Environment and Heritage	2004	Australia
DCRD (Department of Rural and Community Development)	2016	Ireland
DTTAS (Department of Transport, Tourism and Sport)	2018	Ireland
EPGC (The Economic Planning Group of Canada)	2013	Canada
ESRT & WWF Vietnam	2013	Vietnam
European Parliament	2015	Europe
FI (Friends- International)	2018	-

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

INTERREG IVC, European Union, & National Institute for Research and Development in Tourism	2014	Europe
Mairie de Paris	2016	Paris
MBIEDOC (Ministry of Business Innovation & Employment and Department of Conservation)	2019	-
MFCG (Ministry of Finance and Corporate Governance)	2015	Antigua and Barbuda
MTCE (Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy)	2012	Indonesia
MTE (Ministry of Tourism and Entertainment)	2015	Jamaica
NTD (National Department of Tourism)	2016	South Africa
Republic of Rwanda	2009	Rwanda
REST (Responsible Ecological Social Tour)	2003	-
SADC (South Africa Development Community)	2012	South Africa
TFTC (Task Force on Travel & Competitiveness)	2012	USA
The Mountain Institute	2013	-
TIES (The International Ecotourism Society)	2007	Cumberland
TSPC (The Tourism Strategic Planning Committee)	2019	USA
USAID (United States Agency for International Development)	2006	Australia
WALGA (Western Australian Local Government Association)	2019	-
WEF (World Economic Forum)	2020	-
WWF (World Wide Fund for Nature)	2001	-

Table 2: The data categories examined through the survey questionnaire used for the study

Characteristics	Items	Response Type	Results
Demographics	Gender	Dichotomous	Table 3 Table 4 Figure 5
	Age	Ordinal	
	Country of origin	Ordinal	
	Length of experience*	Ratio scale	
	Type of work	Nominal	
Community understanding aspect	Wants	Interval	Figure 2
	Needs	Interval	Figure 3
	CBT planning	Interval	Figure 4
	CBT execution	Interval	
	CBT monitoring and evaluation	Interval	
Work Interest	Local government's interest with communities	Interval	Table 6
	Communities' interest with local government	Interval	
Overall reputation	Government Involvement	Interval	Table 7

As a descriptive quantitative study, data analysis was carried out via IBM SPSS Statistic 21 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). The data analysis process first went through a filtering process to check if the data collected is viable. This process is composed of missing value, normality, and outlier statistics. These three steps filter and check for data irregularity. Descriptive research attempts to determine or describe what a situation is, and descriptive analysis for sociology utilizes the respondents' point of view to understand and explain the research question (Bryman and Cramer, 1996; Hair et al., 2010; Kline., 2015). Missing data models are run to see if the collected data is suitable for multivariate analysis use (Hair et al., 2010; Field, 2013). There are situations where missing data affects patterns or relationship results, hence the need to maintain the original value as

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

much as possible (Groves et al., 2011; Kline, 2015). The process includes checking for data entry errors, deleting individual respondent cases from the list if there are some answers left blank (Hair et al., 2010; Kline, 2015), and is followed by a diagnostic test for the level of randomness.

5. RESULTS

During the spring of 2021, 535 targeted respondents from academia, CBT, government and community development related online fora and groups were contacted (see Table 3 and Table 4). Data are screened based on the respondents work experience with any of the four groups (can overlap): government sectors (422), local community (385), academia (374), and international organizations (339). Some respondents may have had overlapping experience in more than one group, which was helpful in adding weight to this study. The concept is to compare each group's evaluation of their local government's role from their point of view. At the same time, the result of the whole group could help gain a better understanding of the general perceived evaluation of government performance in CBT. In total there are 40 countries recorded, with the United States taking the majority of 15.7% (84). Followed up by Australia at 12.8% (69), Denmark 12.5% (67), Canada 12.1% (65), Germany 12.1% (65), and Nigeria 9.1% (49). Together these countries add up to 74.5% of the total. The next 25.5% is made up of Zambia 4.2% (23), New Zealand 3.5% (19), United Kingdom 3.5 (19), Colombia 2.8% (15), and Mexico 2.4% (13). The remaining 28 countries contributed 8.9% (47). In addition, the demographic data show that age groups 45-54 (170, 32%) and 55-64 (169, 32%) provide the majority of the respondents, followed by 35-44 (110, 21%). The age distribution is followed by the gender distribution male 53% to female 47%. It can also be noted that the older age ranges may have higher experience with and interest in community development than the lower ones. The diversity of the respondents' overall demographic data allows a better analysis of government and CBT evaluation.

Table 3: Demographics of respondents (n=535)

Characteristics		N	%
Gender	Male	283	52.89
	Female	252	47.1
Age Group	18-24	28	5.23
	25-34	35	6.54
	35-44	110	20.56
	45-54	170	31.77
	55-64	169	31.58
	65-74	20	3.73
	75+	3	0.56
Work Experience	Academia	374	60.1
	Government	422	52.71
	International Organization	339	50.65
	Local Community	385	61.49

Table 4: Length of work experience with different groups (n=535)

	Local Community (385)	Local Government (422)	Academia (374)	International Organization (339)
Less than a year	56	68	52	68
1-2 years	98	92	135	102
3-5 years	91	107	127	59
6-9 years	43	85	40	71
10 or more years	97	70	20	39

The types of experience of the respondents of CBT development varies, and some participants have multiple types of experience in different sectors. As shown in Figure 5, those who shared involvement with the local communities have high work

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

experience with 'rural and communities development' (93), 'children, equality, disability' (84), and 'culture, arts, sport, and media' (60). Whereas those who have experience with international organizations have a high amount of experience in 'children, equality, disability' (51), 'environment, climate, and communications' (44), and a tied score for both 'business, enterprise, and innovation' (43) and 'rural communities development' (43). The participants with local government & NGO involvement show also in 'children, equality, disability' (97), 'environment, climate, and communications' (70), and 'education' (64). Lastly, the types of experience that academics have ranges from 'business, enterprise, innovation' (66), 'education' (60), to 'further education, research, science' (47).

The type of experience reflects on the current trend of work distribution among sections of the community and points out which work is more emphasized by each group. People who worked with academia have to be related with business as they need to see how academic research innovation can contribute to community development. All three international organizations, the local communities, and government & NGOs share high experience on the subject of children, disability, and equality. This may suggest that the three groups are currently in the business of defending children, the disabled, and other equality issues in the CBT arena. The international organizations and government & NGOs are both working on the community's environment; this could be because environment and climate as a whole affect groups outside specific communities at the macro scale, and therefore should be more in the hands of a larger organization. Meanwhile, people who worked for the local communities logically demonstrated high effort in working for their development.

Figure 5. Type of Work Experience

Table 6 presents the overall opinions of all respondents regarding their group faction. The reliability analysis shows the item-total correlation and determines if the removal of the item would improve the corresponding alpha values [38]. The alpha score determines if any item were to be removed; the remaining items would still remain at an alpha score above 0.88, a higher score than the acceptable 0.70 standard. The mean score analysis shows that the respondents had strong positive attitude towards local government's involvement in community development projects (2.701). Respondents display strong positive views (2.378) on how local government knows what the local community wants but has less understanding of local needs (2.815). This suggests that local government is aware of the situation of the community for development project. The government's CBT operation is based on its planning (3.088), execution (3.239), and monitoring (3.14). These evaluations of government capability indicates the fairly positive impact the government has on the community, but suggests that although the local government's role does bring changes to development, their power is limited.

The government's interest in working with local communities scored 2.856, and 2.734 if vice-versa. A possible explanation could be because the government are the providers and are in charge of multiple communities, thus making them less keen in cooperating with locals in development projects. Or possibly because complying with the demands of communities

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

could hinder CBT development progress, thus explaining why the government interest in the community is not higher than the reverse situation. Nevertheless, the overall evaluation of government involvement shows a positive score of 2.701; this positive outcome reinforces the concept discussed in the literature that reaching out to local government may be the most practical way to administrate CBT ventures in the initial stage.

Table 6: Reliability test result of overall respondents (n=535)

Variable name and description	Mean (SD)	Items-total correlation	Alpha if items deleted
Understanding of Community			
Government know what local community 'Want'	2.378 (0.861)	0.456	0.883
Government know what local community 'Need'	2.815 (1.095)	0.284	0.884
CBT Operation Stages			
Government's Community Planning Capability	3.088 (1.167)	0.325	0.884
Government's Action Plan Execution Capability	3.239 (1.258)	0.363	0.883
Government's Capability in Monitoring and Reviewing Community Development	3.14 (1.126)	0.342	0.884
Work Interest Between Community and Government			
Government's Interest in Working with Local Community in Community Development	2.856 (1.025)	0.336	0.884
Local Community's Interest in Working with the Government in Community Development	2.734 (0.948)	0.253	0.885
Overall Government Evaluation			
Government Involvement is Helpful	2.701 (1.102)	0.264	0.885

In addition to the results summarized in Table 6, Figures 7-14 compare the question items against each group. This allows further perception of government involvement in CBT from different point of views. Figure 7 demonstrates how much the government & NGOs understand local people's desires. This is depicted in relation to local community (2.32), government and NGOs (2.3), academia (2.26), and international organization (2.25). With a high approval rate of 94%-96% from each group in acknowledging that the government understands what its communities want.

Figure 7. Government & NGOs know what Local People Want

In contrast with *want*, Figure 8 checks if the government & NGOs understand the *needs* of the local people. The average of each group are local community (2.84), government and NGO (2.82), academia (2.81), and international organization group

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

(2.79). The overall ratings show 71%-75%, 20%-22% undecided, and 5%-7% disapproval. Notice the difference between 'undecided' gap for Figure 7 and 8. This may suggest that in the difference between 'want' and 'need', the government may have heard the voices of their people, but to the local communities, the government does not feel that they are well understood.

Government & NGO know what local people "Need"

Figure 8. Government & NGOs know what Local People Need

CBT stages are commonly divided into three phases; planning, execution, and monitoring. The evaluation of the government & NGOs' planning process shown in Figure 9 shows an approval rate of 62%-65% and 70% from the international organization group. The average scores are local communities (3.06), government and NGO (3.06), academia (2.97), and international organizations group (2.89). The outcome suggest that both local community and the local government group have a mutual understanding of the effectiveness of government' planning. Possibly suggest that both parties may have agreed and negotiated beforehand the plans and expectation of CBT.

Government & NGOs' Productivity in CBT "Planning"

Figure 9. Government & NGOs' Productivity in CBT Planning

The execution stage is when the government and NGO take action in constructing their infrastructure, training, and marketing for CBT to operate. It is at this stage the people see the capabilities and support of their government. Figure 10 displays an approval rate of 67%-70%, 14%-15% were undecided, and 16%-19% disapproved. The average scores are local communities (3.12), government and NGO (3.15), academia (3.1), and international organizations group (3.05).

Government & NGOs' Productivity in CBT "Execution"

Figure 10. Government & NGOs' Productivity in CBT Execution

As for government & NGOs' monitoring and review evaluations (Figure 11), the general approval rate indicates a range of 72%-75%, 15%-16 uncertainty, and 10%-12% disapproval. The average scores are local communities (2.94), government and NGO (3.03), academia (2.95), and international organizations group (3.03). This suggests that the role of government & NGOs may not always be to support local people, because the communities are within the government control and are constantly being monitored anyway.

Government & NGO's Productivity in "Monitor and Review"

Figure 11. Government & NGOs' Productivity in CBT Monitoring and Review

In Figure 12, government & NGOs interest in working with local people in CBT development projects has an approval rate of 72%-76%, 18%-23% uncertainty, and a 5%-7% disapproval rate. The average scores are local communities (2.82), government and NGO (2.74), academia (2.75), and international organizations group (2.66).

Government & NGO have Strong Interest in working with "Local People"

Figure 12. Government & NGO Interest in Working with Local People in CBT Development

In Figure 13, the local community’s interest in working with government & NGOs show an approval rate of 77%-80%, undecided at 15%-18%, and 4%-5% disapproval. The average scores are local communities (2.69), government and NGO (2.67), academia (2.67), and international organizations group (2.62).

Local People have Strong Interest in working with "Government & NGO"

Figure13. Local People’s Interest in Working with Government & NGOs in CBT Development

Figure 14 displays the helpfulness evaluation of government & NGOs involvement in CBT. The average scores are local communities (2.54), government and NGO (2.61), academia (2.57), and international organizations group (2.57). The helpfulness ratio shows 75%-79% to 11%-13% undecided, and 1%-2% opposing, an average of 2.64. Almost a quarter claimed this group as very helpful. The results show a higher positivity by government & NGOs than academia for overall CBT evaluation.

Helpfulness to CBT: Government & NGOs' Involvement

Figure14. Helpfulness in CBT: Government & NGOs Involvement

6. DISCUSSION

From the data, the community and government groups tend to have similar score on most of the questionnaire items. The understanding of the community’s want and needs for instance showed how both local community and government groups rated 2.3 and 2.8 for want and needs. This indicates that the government does indeed know less about the needs of the community than it perhaps should. The CBT operation stages are positive though but are at a scale of 3; planning (3.06), execution (3.1), and monitoring (3.0). This could suggest that both local community and government group sees the government’s capability to support CBT operations as adequate and even slightly above average. The possible reason for this suggests that the government’s resource is only limited, and thus during each operation, covering the basic infrastructure and training would be enough to administrate CBT projects. The work interest between government and local community shows how the government group perceived the government to be more passionate in mutual work interest (2.74 and 2.67) than the local community group (2.82 and 2.69). This result may suggest that the government may have perceived local people to have a higher desire to work with their government as they have the power and resources to provide for the community. However why the wiliness of locals to work with the government is not higher may probably be due to local belief that the government, while it could provide the necessary support for CBT projects, this might not be at a satisfactory level or wat for that the community. In turn, this may be supported by the difference between average wants and needs discussed above.

The academic and international organization groups provide a third party neutral perspective on the relationship between local government and local community. Although all four groups are similar, the academic and international organization groups perceived most factors as being stronger than either the government or community groups. Furthermore, the international organization shows the strongest sense in believing that the government knows the wants (2.25) and needs (2.79) of community. CBT operation stages evaluation graded by academia and international organizations showed a better outcome than either government or community groups. This might suggest that, from the exterior point of view, the government’s role in CBT operations should be more efficient than expected. The international organization group perceives the work interest between both government and local community to be the strongest among all groups (2.66 and 2.62). In summary, the results show how third parties such as academia or international organizations can overestimate the government’s capability in CBT operations. On the contrary the government group evaluated itself as the weakest in CBT operations, implying that the respondents’ understanding of the government structure flow may have interior issues that hinder their progress.

7. LIMITATIONS

Further study should compare the academic and international organizations’ CBT evaluation, as these two groups are also known to publish CBT guidelines and these can be found in the existing literature. A qualitative method through focus groups or interviews with government representatives may provide further insights on the relationship between government and community.

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

8. CONCLUSIONS

This study examines local government involvement in CBT development from the perception of respondents with work experience in the government, community, academia, and international organization sectors. CBT is a trending alternate method for communities to become sustainable on their own through maximizing tourism revenue. From the literature, the role of local government is to design plans and guidelines to introduce tourism to its community members. At times, the government will collaborate with NGOs to tailor specific instructions for a particular community. This study gathered various guidelines written by different governments and NGOs, and through MAXQDA word cloud software, the outcome showed that most frequent phases in this are action plans; community development; decision making; economic growth; international tourism; local communities; natural resources; private sector; product development; sustainable development; tourism planning; and monitoring. These keywords were used as key indicators for questionnaire design. Further observation reveals that these keywords are often mentioned with community's understanding of the bond between locals and government. The guidelines may have different strategies but the majority had three common instructions for building CBT: 1) planning, 2) plan execution, and 3) monitoring and evaluation.

After this content analysis, an online survey was distributed and collected in the Spring of 2021 to fora and groups in the field of CBT and community development. Work experience with either local government, community, academia, or international organization was a major factor in filtering the data, as these respondents present more insights on the involvement of government in CBT development. A 7-point Likert scale was used for the respondents to evaluate if their government understands the people's want and needs, and the findings show governments have a higher understanding of local community's wants (2.37), but a lower understanding of the people's needs (2.81). The three stages of government's CBT development capabilities are evaluated, with planning (3.08), execution (3.23), and monitoring (3.14) being the results. The government's work interest with the local community (2.85) is not as high as the local community's interest with the government (2.73). The community's overall evaluation of the government's involvement (2.7) in CBT projects is positive.

The results of this study show that the perspective of local community groups tends to rate the government understands and capability of CBT projects as mildly positive. The respondents that worked in the government sector rated the government's capabilities as the weakest among all other groups, yet the international organization group rated the opposite. This phenomenon could be explained by how third parties evaluated the closeness of the relationship between government and its communities. Whereas those that are involved understand the limits of the government sector with regard to development. The reason that government fails in CBT development can be due to how this sector tends to emphasize the tourism revenue rather than catering for social issues (Wilkinson, 1979; DCLG, 2006). The work interest between government and local community is expected to be stronger by third parties; this existing gap could reinforce the concept by Kretzman and McKnight (1993) that where the community would see themselves as clients in relying on government support, the government instead sees distributing resources to communities as an obligation.

However, for CBT to be a functional enterprise, community participation and involvement is necessary, if a community lacks the motive to participate in CBT transformation, the program may not be suitable for the community in the first place. On the other hand, CBT needs startup funding for initial development, thus community members might see the government as difficult if the community's proposals are constantly rejected. Rather than pushing and marketing the community for tourism profit, the government's role should be more open and welcoming for the community to approach them to discuss about plans and funding. Doing so allows the government to place themselves as investors and enables their observation of the community willingness for CBT development when they have to decide if further support is needed.

REFERENCES

- 1) Braden, S., & Mayo, M. (1999). Culture, community development and representation. *Community Development Journal*, 34(3), 191-204.
- 2) Bryman, A., & Cramer, D. (1996). Quantitative data analysis with minitab: a guide for social scientists. Psychology Press.
- 3) Byrne, J. P. (2002). Two cheers for gentrification. *Howard LJ*, 46, 405.
- 4) DCLG (Department of Communities and Local Government). (2006). *The Community Development Challenge*. London: HM Government.
- 5) Duany, A. (2001). Three Cheers for "Gentrification". *The American Enterprise*, 12(3), 36-36.
- 6) Green, G. P., & Goetting, A. (2010). Community assets: Building the capacity for development. *Mobilizing communities: Asset building as a community development strategy*, 1-13.

An Evaluation Study of The Role of Government in Community Based-Tourism Development

- 7) Hair, J. F., Anderson, R. E., Babin, B. J., & Black, W. C. (2010). Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective (Vol. 7).
- 8) Kaur, P., Jawaid, A., & Othman, N. B. A. (2016). The Impact of Community-Based Tourism on Community Development in Sarawak. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(1), 15-26.
- 9) Kerstein, R. (1990). Stage models of gentrification: an examination. *Urban Affairs Quarterly*, 25(4), 620-639.
- 10) Kline, R. B. (2015). Principles and practice of structural equation modeling. Guilford publications.
- 11) Kontogeorgopoulos, N., Churyen, A., & Duangsaeng, V. (2014). Success factors in community- based tourism in Thailand: The role of luck, external support, and local leadership. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 11(1), 106–124.
- 12) Kretzmann, J. P., & McKnight, J. (1993). *Building communities from the inside out* (pp. 2-10). Evanston, IL: Center for Urban Affairs and Policy Research, Neighborhood Innovations Network.
- 13) Newman, K., & Wyly, E. K. (2006). The right to stay put, revisited: Gentrification and resistance to displacement in New York City. *Urban studies*, 43(1), 23-57.
- 14) Smith, N. (2000) 'Gentrification', in R.J. Johnston, D. Gregory, G. Pratt, and M. Watts (eds.) *e Dictionary of Human Geography* 4th ed. (Oxford: Blackwell) 294–296.
- 15) Tasci, A. D. (2011). Destination branding and positioning. *Destination marketing and management: Theories and applications*, 113-129.
- 16) Wilkinson, K. P. (1972). A field-theory perspective for community development research. *Rural Sociology*, 37(1), 43.
- 17) WWF (World Wildlife Fund). (2001). *Guidelines for community- based ecotourism development*. Gland, Switzerland: WWF International.